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Coco Mellors' *Blue Sisters*

Reviewed by
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THE SUNDAY TIMES BESTSELLING AUTHOR OF CLEOPATRA AND FRANKENSTEIN

COCO MELLORS

Blue Sisters

'Captivating'
TESS GUNTY

'Richly textured'
ISABEL KAPLAN

'Gorgeous'
RAVEN LEILANI

Blue Sisters | Novel | Coco Mellors |
Harper Collins, Great Britain, 2024

American author Coco Mellors' second novel *Blue Sisters*, delves deep into the world of women. It demands to strip away the heavy burden of patriarchy after creating a strong bond between sisters. She strives to demonstrate through her portrayed characters that 'the feeling that to be a girl with other girls was not some weakness, as they had been told, but a power, the best and luckiest power on earth' (220). The world of women is compassionate. A filial relation among women can work as a healing balm that can tenderly cure the wounds. In this patriarchal society, where women are always said to be enemies of each other, possessing jealousy and hatred, sisterhood creates a strong bond between women. Their shared feelings, emotions, and tantrums without judging each other can bring harmony and kinship. But in reality, is it really possible? Because the world is believed to maintain the detestation and resentment between women. Coco Mellors' Book *Blue Sisters* is one of the examples, which starts with the same loathing and animosity among sisters. But the ending culminates with love, devotion and affection for each other.

Sisterhood or the filial bond between women is not a new concept, though. There are a good number of novels that portray this relationship. But highlighting this relationship in the academic discussion concords with women's bondage. In the face of patriarchy, women developed strong relationships as social and emotional support networks in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. In a society that mistreated them because of their gender identity, these relationships—often referred to as sororal bonding—were a means of maintaining their identity. The strong emotional attachment was seen to be at the core of these bonds. As the women's rights movement gained momentum in the 19th and early 20th centuries, sisterhood became more than just friendships and personal bonds with the rise of the second wave of feminism. Women's associations and organisations played a key role in the fight for women's suffrage, labour rights, and educational reform. Feminists established sisterhood as a political term after realising the importance of group action.

By this time, sisterhood had spread beyond politics to include consciousness-raising organisations. Now, the purpose of this relationship between women was to create female role models and distance themselves from the male influence in their lives. With the addition of pecuniary and activist backing, the sisterhood's original emotional intimacy was somewhat restored.

In an effort to improve sisterhoods' inclusivity and consideration of identity intersections, including colour, ethnicity, sexual orientation, class, etc., the third wave of feminism emerged to rectify the flaws of the earlier movements. But this was also the period when the phrase itself, which was primarily linked to second-wave feminism, came under fire for its reduction of the varied experiences of women and exclusion of males. Despite some people's disbelief in fourth-wave feminism, sisterhood has resurfaced in popularity, but with slightly altered definitions due to its purported origin and the growth of social media. It now encompasses men, transgender individuals, people of colour, and other disadvantaged groups, and it is founded on people's varied experiences rather than their shared oppression and hardships.

Coco Mellors creates sisterhood between blood-related sisters and also between lesbian women with the purpose of conscious rising. The four sisters in this novel are Avery, Bonnie, Nicky and Lucky. Among them, Nicky dies early. She was suffering from chronic pain due to endometriosis. She lives only in memories and flashbacks of the other three sisters. But through the life involvement of the other three sisters, Mellors desperately tries to raise their self-consciousness with the intention of personal growth and maturation to re-identify themselves.

The book revolves around twelve chapters with a prologue and epilogue. Each chapter is named after the sisters, and among them, the oldest sister, a lawyer by profession, is Avery. She has been married to Chiti, a therapist, for ten years and is also a lesbian. They both develop a solid and stable partnership and feel comfortable in their relationship, with enough space, freedom, and choice. But after 10 years of their marriage, it breaks up as Aver

cheats on her wife with a man, Charlie, with whom she sleeps one day just to satisfy her sexual desire. The desire Avery longs for, which Chiti fails to provide, makes Avery seek another option. Moreover, she does not want to have any babies in her married life with Chiti because she does not want to hamper her career, and at the same time, she observes her mother's poor condition after being a mother. But she repents for her deed at last because one day's sexual thirst seems heavy on her heart. Charlie satisfies her desire, but fails to comfort her mentally, which Avery needs most during her critical time with her sisters.

Avery is a responsible woman who, in order to protect her sisters, becomes possessive, arrogant and selfish. At her age of thirty-three, she realises that it is necessary and important 'to grow into your own woman' (180) to realise and understand the harsh realities of patriarchy. She knows that time is more powerful than money. She wants success in life with her profession. Like her mother, she can't limit herself to the family only, and therefore, she does not want to have any babies with Chiti. She believes motherhood is a tough phase, 'becoming a mother is a shocking thing. Like landing on the moon. Everything changes' (220). She finds herself in her own career.

Bonnie is the second sister who is a boxing enthusiast, which is never supported by her mother but always by her father. He supports and appreciates her because he wants to have a son. Bonnie is calm and placid in nature. She loves and understands others well. She works as the bouncer for Peachy's, a nearby bar. She takes care of her other little sisters, but she blames herself completely for the death of her sister Nicky because when Nicky overdosed, she took Nicky to the hospital and witnessed her death helplessly. Bonnie believes in God, and she finds herself in it.

The third sister is Nicky, who, throughout the novel, lives in memories of her sisters only. Nicky dies early at the age of 26. She is a perfect example of a normal woman who is soft spoken and always aspires to have her husband and babies. She has a friendly nature and loves branded shopping and being with rich friends.

When she died, she was a school teacher by profession. Tune into motherhood is a form of freedom where pain is there, but also with pleasure, Nicky used to believe that. The death of Nicky shakes the other members of her family. The diameter of their relationship changes, and everyone thinks themselves responsible for this tragedy and gradually detaches themselves from each other. The most shocking impact happens with Lucky, the last sister, and she is the jolliest and perverted one. Lucky is addicted to smoking and alcohol, which is resulted from her family tragedy and also her father's gruesome brutality after drinking. Lucky is just two years younger than Nicky, and both leave as twins. Lucky lives a vagabond life and cuts all her family relationships after losing her sister.

But the three sisters meet again after one year when they receive news from their mother about the sale of their house. Their mother wants them to come back and take their necessary items before the house is auctioned off. Their mother is also a victim of patriarchy who decides to sell the house to treat her husband, who is in rehab, suffering from liver disease after an excessive amount of drinking. She remains silent throughout her life under the strong regime of her husband due to her inability to give birth to a son. Gradually, she starts to hate her daughters. This detestation takes her daughters far away from her. The woman, into her she fails to recapitulate. This hurts her the most and also makes her sentiment towards her daughters. At the end of the novel, we find her spending life in an upstate where she turns into a very ugly woman, cutting all the social life.

After her last meeting with Avery, she confesses all her lifelong pains and tantrums. She believes that keeping herself separated from her daughters actually helps them to grow psychologically strong and stable. She teaches Avery to believe in nothing 'but a woman's capacity to survive disappointment' (212).

Thus, Mellors tries to give a beautiful portrait of sisterhood through the three characters. The mother-daughter relationship has also been positioned strongly here. But the sisterly bond is

highlighted more by the author. Their psychological struggle to be a woman, their initial hatred towards each other that later transforms into love and affection to create a strong emotional bond eventually, is beautifully portrayed by her. Not only that, each sister, while loving and sympathising with each other, finds their own selves as well. They calculate the meaning and true value of self-love. As the book has discussed a serious issue in society, this book is well intended for scholars of feminism and women's issues. The book is a good example of a healthy relationship between women, which is desperately needed in today's society in order to lessen the patriarchy and its stronghold. Mellors has created a strong role model of the bond through her portrayal of the three characters to bring harmony and solace.